

Measuring Cash and Banking Access Vulnerability: A Composite Small-Area Index Integrating Infrastructure and Population Characteristics

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Summary

Current UK cash access monitoring relies on Euclidean distance thresholds that treat infrastructure gaps as the sole determinant of exclusion. This paper develops the Cash and Banking Vulnerability Index (CABVI), integrating network-based accessibility with population vulnerability across 43,914 UK small areas. Using Valhalla routing with OpenStreetMap, we apply differential exponential decay functions for distinct infrastructure types. Demand-side indicators encompass age, health/disability, income deprivation, and digital exclusion derived through geodemographic linkage. Results reveal regional clustering in post-industrial Northern England and Northern Ireland, with substantial intra-urban variation demonstrating that aggregate statistics mask neighbourhood-level disparities, challenging uniform distance-based policy responses.

KEYWORDS: accessibility analysis; composite indices; network routing; geodemographics; financial inclusion

1. Introduction

The UK's physical cash infrastructure has been fundamentally reshaped, with thousands of bank branches closing since 2015 and ATM availability declining by 5% in 2024 to approximately 46,182 LINK ATMs, of which 37,361 are free-to-use (LINK, 2025). The Post Office network has become increasingly significant, now constituting over 65% of all branch-based cash access points nationally. Shared banking hubs managed by Cash Access UK provide services in communities that have lost their last bank branch, with 178 hubs operational by August 2025.

The Financial Services and Markets Act 2023 granted the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) powers to ensure reasonable access to cash. Current FCA monitoring indicates over 95% of the population remains within government-set distances (one mile urban, three miles rural) of free-to-use cash withdrawal points. However, these straight-line metrics are acknowledged to overestimate coverage by ignoring real-world transport networks (FCA, 2025). Ennis and Bogiatzis-Gibbons (2025) found that predictive models for cash reliance demonstrated only acceptable predictive power, concluding such models would not be suitable for local area prediction.

Cash reliance varies substantially across populations: lower-income households use it for budgeting, people with disabilities face digital accessibility barriers, and older adults often prefer tangible payment methods. Research demonstrates strong links between digital and financial exclusion (Yates et al., 2020). Drawing on relational geographies of finance (Leyshon and Thrift, 1997), we conceptualise vulnerability as emerging from the intersection of infrastructure provision and population

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characteristics rather than infrastructure gaps alone. This paper develops the Cash and Banking Vulnerability Index (CABVI), addressing the gap between simple distance-based monitoring and tools that identify where infrastructure gaps most severely compromise financial inclusion.

2. Methodology

2.1 Geographic Units and Infrastructure Data

The target geography comprises 43,914 small areas from 2021/22 Census geographies: Lower-layer Super Output Areas (England and Wales, 1,000-3,000 residents), Data Zones (Scotland, 500-1,000 residents), and Small Areas (Northern Ireland, ~1,700 residents). These units balance granularity with statistical reliability. Population-weighted centroids serve as origin points for accessibility calculations. Where input data were available only for 2011 Census geographies, population-weighted centroids of 2021/22 zones were used to assign scores.

Cash infrastructure data were compiled from multiple sources: LINK ATM snapshot data (June 2025) for all free-to-use machines; Post Office locations with personal banking functions under the Banking Framework; and UK Banking Hubs (open or temporarily operational) from Cash Access UK. Bank and building society branches were extracted from institutional websites and geocoded using the HERE API. Banking Hub locations replaced co-located Post Offices to avoid double-counting. Two key assumptions underpin these data: locations are available and open (though branches have limited hours and banking hubs serve specific banks on particular days), and brand neutrality for cash access (though banking services require specific provider relationships).

2.2 Demand-Side Vulnerability Indicators

Four demand-side components capture population vulnerability based on established determinants of cash reliance. **Age** (D_i): proportion aged 65+ from 2022 mid-year population estimates (England, Wales, Northern Ireland) or 2022 Census (Scotland), scaled to $[0,1]$. **Income deprivation** (I_i) and **health/disability deprivation** (H_i): binary indicators ($\in\{0,1\}$) for areas in the top 20% of nation-specific Index of Multiple Deprivation domains. This threshold aligns with UK government targeting conventions and was validated using FCA Financial Lives Survey data, which showed top-20% most deprived areas had index scores 15-52% above national average for cash-related difficulties.

Digital exclusion (G_i): No UK-wide small-area measure exists, so we linked FCA Financial Lives Survey responses to the UK Output Area Classification (OAC). The FCA defines digitally excluded as individuals who have not used the Internet in three months or used it less than weekly and rate their ability as poor. Index scores (base=100) were generated for each of OAC's 21 groups. Target areas were defined where digital exclusion rates exceeded 20% above national average, encompassing 22% of areas including Challenged Multicultural Communities and Students (index=214), Routine Occupations or Retirement (178), and Ethnically Diverse Families in Less Connected Locations (161).

2.3 Supply-Side Accessibility Calculation

Network routing was calculated using the Valhalla routing engine with UK OpenStreetMap data, providing network-based accessibility rather than Euclidean distances. Cash access was measured as the count of free-to-use ATMs (n_i) within a 10-minute walk (~800m at average walking speed), consistent with retail catchment analysis thresholds (Dolega et al., 2016). Bank branch access used counts (m_i) within 20-minute public transport journey times, following UK government accessibility standards (Department for Transport, 2014).

Access counts were converted to risk scores using exponential decay functions that operationalise the insight that different access points support distinct, partially non-substitutable financial practices. For ATMs: $A_i^{\text{risk}} = 1$ if $n_i=0$, otherwise $1-\exp(-\lambda/n_i)$. Similarly for branches: $B_i^{\text{risk}} = 1$ if $m_i=0$, otherwise $1-\exp(-\mu/m_i)$. Risk is maximal (1) when no access exists and falls as more machines/branches become

available. Decay parameters were calibrated using half-risk thresholds: $\lambda = n_{50} \times \ln(2)$ with $n_{50}=2$ for ATMs, reflecting infrastructural redundancy (backup availability when one machine is out-of-service), and $\mu = m_{50} \times \ln(2)$ with $m_{50}=1$ for branches, reflecting their more comprehensive functionality for deposits, complex transactions, and advisory services.

2.4 Composite Index Construction

The final CABVI balances demand and supply components: $CABVI_i = W_D \times \bar{D}_i + W_S \times \bar{S}_i$, where $\bar{D}_i = (D_i + I_i + H_i + G_i)/4$ and $\bar{S}_i = (A_i^{risk} + B_i^{risk})/2$. This addresses the asymmetry between four demand and two supply inputs. Equal weighting ($W_D=W_S=0.5$) ensures vulnerability requires both need and inadequate provision to coexist, though weights can be adjusted for alternative policy priorities ($W_D>0.5$ for needs-based targeting; $W_S>0.5$ for infrastructure gap prioritisation).

3. Results

CABVI scores demonstrate substantial geographic heterogeneity (mean=0.437, SD=0.165, range=0.019-0.955, IQR=0.232). Two distinct spatial patterns emerge: peripheral areas exhibit elevated vulnerability where constrained infrastructure amplifies demand-side factors, while urban cores display substantial heterogeneity with high and low vulnerability in close spatial proximity.

Figure 1: CABVI Scores for the UK

Local authority aggregation reveals pronounced regional clustering. Highest-vulnerability authorities include Halton (mean=0.580), Knowsley (0.571) which are both within Liverpool City Region (see Figure 2), and Derry City and Strabane (0.568), indicating systematic challenges across entire districts. Northern Ireland shows disproportionate representation (three of top ten nationally), while post-industrial English authorities including Rotherham (0.547), Middlesbrough (0.547), and Oldham (0.538) also rank highly. This clustering reflects shared vulnerability drivers: deindustrialisation legacies, demographic aging, and commercial banking retreat. Greater London dominates low-vulnerability rankings, with nine of ten least vulnerable authorities being London boroughs and the City of London showing exceptional resilience (mean=0.109).

Figure 2 CABVI Within Liverpool City Region

Analysis at finer spatial resolution reveals substantial intra-urban variation that local authority aggregates obscure. Glasgow City exhibits extreme within-authority heterogeneity ($SD=0.23$, $range=0.91$ across 786 Data Zones), spanning near-minimum to near-maximum CABVI values within a single administrative boundary. In contrast, Fermanagh and Omagh demonstrate uniformly elevated vulnerability ($mean=0.56$, $SD=0.12$), indicating systematic challenges stemming from rural geography, sparse population, and peripheral location rather than internal socioeconomic differentiation. This contrast has direct policy implications: heterogeneous authorities like Glasgow require spatially-targeted interventions calibrated to neighbourhood-specific conditions, while homogeneous high-vulnerability authorities may benefit from authority-wide strategies addressing systematic infrastructure deficits.

4. Conclusions

The CABVI framework demonstrates the value of integrating network-based accessibility with geodemographic vulnerability indicators at small-area scale. The substantial intra-urban variation identified validates the need for fine-grained spatial analysis that aggregate statistics obscure. Our finding that identical service configurations generate vastly different vulnerability levels depending on local population characteristics challenges regulatory approaches based on universal distance thresholds. The framework provides an evidence-based tool for identifying where infrastructure gaps most severely compromise financial inclusion, supporting place-sensitive rather than uniform policy responses. Future development could incorporate longitudinal tracking as infrastructure changes, integration with qualitative case studies in high-vulnerability areas, and sensitivity analysis of weighting schemes for different policy objectives.

5. References

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6. Biography

Alex Singleton is Professor of Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool and Director of the Geographic Data Service. His research sits at the boundary between the social and computational sciences; and has extended a tradition of area classification within Urban Analytics where he has developed an empirically informed critique of the ways in which geodemographic methods (unsupervised machine learning) can be refined for effective yet ethical use; and how systems comprising artificial intelligence can assist in public resource allocation applications. This research has developed from substantive interests around the social, spatial and temporal dimensions of urban systems; specifically focused on inequalities of opportunities.